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Does the Consumption of Immune Boosting Foods Influence the Body Mass Index in College Going Students?

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Optimal immune status results from a good balanced nutrition and a physically active lifestyle, ensuring a normal body mass index. The main objective of the present study is to expound the relationship between the Body Mass Index and the intake of specific immune boosting foods. **Materials and Methods:** 211 college going students in the age group of 18 to 30 years participated in this cross-sectional study. A web-based tool was designed to collect data on anthropometric measurements and food frequency of immune boosting foods such as tea, ginger, garlic and turmeric intake. Ethical clearance was approved from the place of study. **Results:** The analysis of BMI data indicated that 62.0% of the study participants had a BMI within the normal range (between 18.5 and 24.9), 13.3% were overweight (between 25 and 29.9), and 3.3% were obese. Nineteen per cent of males and 41.2% of females had a WHR above normal. Thirty eight per cent and 34.1 per cent used garlic daily and three days a week, respectively, with a BMI within the normal range ($p < 0.05$). 54.5% and 23.7% used turmeric daily and three days a week, respectively, likewise, 39.8% and 31.3% used ginger daily and three days a week, respectively and had a normal BMI. However, the results showed no statistical significance for turmeric, ginger and tea. **Conclusion:** Regular consumption of immune boosting foods like turmeric, ginger and garlic may have influenced the body mass index of the study participants.

Keywords: Body Mass Index, Ginger, garlic, turmeric, tea, immune boosting foods.

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Introduction

Body Mass Index (BMI) is popularly used; it is the simplest anthropometric parameter. The widely used BMI classification to assess nutritional status is given by the WHO.¹ BMI plays a pivotal role in immuno-modulatory activities. Generally, interventions such as a low calorie diet, moderate physical activity, a healthy lifestyle, eliminating smoking and alcohol and engaging in activities to lower stress are positive approaches towards maintaining an optimum Body Mass Index. However, the contributions of immune boosting foods cannot be devalued. The presence of bioactive components in these foods plays a definitive role in bringing about a favourable body weight. From several research studies, a total of eight herbs and spices were found to have a positive effect on BMI, waist circumference and body weight.² A few of these are included in this study namely turmeric, ginger, garlic and tea. Furthermore, a close relationship between the BMI and usage of individual immune boosting foods like turmeric, ginger, garlic and tea was demonstrated^{3,4,5,6}, which reinforces the claims by previous studies that these foods are anti-obesity as they bring about a significant weight change. Literature is scarce on the frequency of intake of immune boosting foods and their relationship to Body Mass Index. Hence, this study is carried forward with the primary objective of assessing the

Body Mass Index of the study participants and expounding the relationship between BMI and the intake of specific immune boosting foods to bridge the existing gap.

Methodology

A well-structured questionnaire was developed and subjected to a pilot study for validation. The study was carried out in the urban setting of Shillong city of Meghalaya, North East India for a period of two months. The demographic information namely age, tribe, education and other socioeconomic details like income, job profile and lifestyle details likesmoking, alcohol and physical activity levels, and medical history of diet related diseases were collected from the study participants. Nutritional Assessment were done following standardized protocol as per ICMR guidelines.⁷ The Anthropometric particulars collected include height, weight, Body Mass Index (BMI) and the Waist to Hip Ratio (WHR). A Food Frequency Questionnaire was developed to collect information on specific indigenous foods such as tea, ginger, garlic and turmeric consumption among the study participants.

The study was given ethical clearance from the place of study. Informed consent was obtained from the study participants before the study was conducted. The inclusion criteria were college going students both males and females in the age group of 18 to 23 years and native tribals without diet related disorders. The exclusion criteria were those who belonged to other states, non-tribals and those who had diet related disorders or with medical intervention. The SPSS statistical software version 24 was used for data analysis. Data analysis was done for descriptive statistics using means and standard deviations (SD). The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used to check the normality of the data. Pearson’s correlation coefficient was used to see if there is any correlation between BMI and immune boosting foods. The ANOVA test was performed to analyse the effect of the immune boosting foods on the different groups of BMI.

Results

A descriptive analysis was used to expound the relationship between the BMI and the intake of selected immune boosting foods namely turmeric, ginger, garlic and tea. A total of 215 young college-going students participated in the study, of which 211 completed the questionnaire. 33.6% were males, and 66.4% were females. The data was normally distributed.

Table-1 indicates the cut-off value of Body Mass Index as given by WHO and the anthropometric measurements of the study participants revealed that 62.1% of them had an optimum Body Mass Index (18.5 to 24.9), 21.3% of the study participants were underweight, 13.2% of them were overweight and a meager 3.0% of them were obese. None had a Body Mass Index above forty. Turmeric powder is a spice used only in cooking, 54.5% and 23.7% of the study participants used it daily and thrice a week, respectively, accounting for the most (78.2%) frequent usage of this spice in the diet among those who had an optimum BMI (Figure 1).

Table-1: Body Mass Index of the selected study participants

Body Mass Index (BMI) Range	No.	%
<18.5	45	21.3
18.5 – 24.9	131	62.1
25 – 29.9	28	13.2
30 – 39.9	7	3.3
>40	0	0
Total	211	100

Source: WHO 2004¹

Figure 1. Frequency of Turmeric Powder Usage of the Selected Study Participants

Only eight per cent of the study participants used turmeric daily in the underweight category and about 2.0% of the obese individuals had turmeric daily in their diet. Raw turmeric tuber was used among this population not as a spice but for medicinal purposes. Among the study participants having a normal BMI, 25.6% used the tuber occasionally whenever required, whereas 11.8% used it almost daily. Only less than two per cent of the obese participants used the tuber occasionally (Fig.-2).

Figure 2. Frequency of Turmeric Tuber Usage of the Selected Study Participants

Ginger is a popular spice used in this region. It is grown in abundance in the state. It contains the highest amount of the bioactive component Zingerol as compared to all varieties found in the entire Northeastern region. Among the participants having a normal BMI, twenty seven per cent and nineteen per cent of the study participants used ginger daily and three times a week, respectively in their daily diet, this (Figure 3) shows that 46.0% of them, ginger is the most frequent spice featuring in their diet.

Figure 3. Frequency of Ginger Usage of the Selected Study Participants

Eight per cent of the underweight participants used it daily and only 0.4% of the obese use ginger daily in their diet. Garlic is one of the spices used for cooking a variety of dishes as well as for medicinal purposes. Almost 47.0% of the study participants having a normal BMI used garlic daily (25.6%) and three times a week (21.0) in their diet. Thirteen per cent of the underweight participants used garlic in their diet daily (4.7%) and three times a week (8.5%), respectively. Only around two per cent of the obese individuals used garlic daily (1.4%) and three times a week (0.9%) respectively (Figure 4.)

Figure 4. Frequency of Garlic Usage of the Selected Study Participants

Figure 5 indicates that fortyone per cent of the study participants with a normal Body Mass Index had 1-2 cups of tea daily, and 20.0% consumed 3 to 4 cups of tea daily and had a normal BMI. However, all (3.3%) of the obese category had tea daily (2.4%) and three times a week (0.9%), respectively. Only 1.4 per cent of the underweight participants had more than six cups of tea daily.

Figure 5. Quantified Frequency of Tea Usage of the Selected Study Participants

Table-2: Effect of Immune Boosting Foods on Different Groups of BMI (ANOVA)

BMI	Immune Boosting Foods on Different Groups of BMI - Mean ± SD					F (df = 3,207)	p
	Underweight	Normal	Overweight	Obese	Total		
Turmeric tuber	1.56±1.700	1.76±1.828	2.29±1.979	1.14±1.069	1.76±1.808	1.258	0.290
Spice Turmeric powder	3.62±1.585	4.08±1.439	4.00±1.563	3.86±1.676	3.96±1.496	1.048	0.372
Spice Ginger	3.49±1.646	3.80±1.459	3.64±1.393	3.14±1.676	3.69±1.498	.831	0.478
Spice Garlic	3.11±1.668	3.84±1.380	3.86±1.458	4.14±0.900	3.70±1.468	3.227	0.023*
Total Spices	1.80±0.815	1.96±0.845	2.14±0.803	1.71±0.756	1.94±0.832	1.184	0.317
Tea	1.49±0.661	1.34±.535	1.39±0.629	1.37±0.575	1.37±0.575	0.854	0.466

Note: Significant results *(p<0.05) highlighted in bold.

Discussion

This study explores the nutritional status of young adults, also attempting to expound the relationship between the immune boosting foods consumed and their impact on the body mass index (BMI). The hypothesis tested was that the frequency of consumption of turmeric, ginger, garlic and tea had no impact on the BMI. It was observed that the majority (62.1%) of both males and females had a normal BMI in the range of 18.5 to 24.9 this is in line with the NFHS 5 findings⁸, which reported a normal BMI in the majority (77.0%) of both men and women. Twenty five per cent of male and 60.0% of female participants had an increased risk of metabolic complications as their waist to hip ratio was higher than normal. This finding, too, supported the NFHS report, which reported that 24.0% of males and 55.0% of females had a WHR at an increased risk for metabolic complications in urban areas of Meghalaya.

The findings of the study is supported by previous studies conducted in similar lines.^{9,10,12,15,16,22} However, this study is unique as it studied the frequency of the intake of individual immune boosting foods and tested its impact on the BMI. Diet is one of the significant contributors to weight, and several foods have been identified to have potential anti-obesity components. Natural foods derived from plants are widely researched to prevent or manage obesity. The study observed the frequency of consumption of both turmeric tuber and turmeric powder among the study participants who had a normal BMI was very high (50%), the spice was used both in cooking and for medicinal purposes but was not statistically significant (turmeric tuber $p=0.290$, turmeric powder $p=0.372$). Turmeric tuber was preferred for medicinal usage during coughs, usually mixed with honey. Recent studies revealed the significant impact of curcumin on BMI and body weight compared to the control or placebo groups.^{9,10} and, to a considerable extent, the anthropometric parameters in obese individuals and adiposity-related adipokines.¹¹

In this study, majority (46.0%) of the study participants who used ginger daily and three times a week were within the normal range of BMI. In several animal models of obesity, *Zingiber officinale* exhibited a weight lowering effect, and this was due to the intervention using ginger extract or its bioactive compound instead of ginger powder.¹² Supplementation with >1500mg/d of ginger for a period of more than eight weeks observed a regulation in both lipid levels and BMI^{13,14}.

Furthermore, in this study, garlic appears to be frequent in the daily diet of normal BMI study participants. Pearson's Correlation and ANOVA showed a positive correlation between the frequent usage of garlic and the BMI ($p<0.05$). The results from 15 randomised controlled trials revealed positive outcomes of garlic intake on body weight, BMI and waist circumference¹⁵ without advocating garlic as a strategy for weight loss and maintaining BMI.¹⁶ Observations from several randomised controlled trials advocated garlic supplementation in reducing anthropometric indices such as waist circumference and BMI^{17,18}.

Tea, another promising immune boosting food ingredient, has the potential to bring about a significant reduction in BMI, glucose and lipid levels among obese individuals.¹⁹ The polyphenols and caffeine in tea are believed to reduce body weight and central body fat among regular tea consumers.²⁰ Tea is considered an anti-obesity food component due to the mechanism that causes a reduction in nutrient digestion and absorption, an increase in energy expenditure, promotion of catabolism of lipids, inhibition of synthesis and modulation of lipids and adipocytes, respectively, the nervous and endocrine systems, and gut microbiota²¹. Intake of tea extract, irrespective of the type of tea, has been found to reduce BMI lipid levels and increase HDL cholesterol and glucose levels²². In obese individuals with metabolic syndrome observed from major randomised controlled trials^{19,22}. Recommendations from studies suggested 600 to 900mg of catechins or three to four cups of strong tea for a minimum period of 8 weeks for a significant reduction in weight and metabolic syndrome.²³ In this study, two to four cups of tea were used by 40 per cent and three to four cups by 20.0% of the study participants with a normal BMI, respectively however, the results did not show any statistical significance ($p=0.466$). The total frequency of all the selected spices was also tested but showed no statistical significance ($p=0.317$) (Table 2).

The prevalence of overweight (13.2%) and obesity (3.3%) in the present study was acceptably lower in this tribal population. The average amount of turmeric used by the study participant was less than half a teaspoon, amounting to about 3 grams. An average of ten to fifteen grams of ginger and garlic was used daily. It has been observed that they included immune boosting foods like turmeric (both powder and tuber 48 per cent), ginger (27.0%), garlic (25.6%) and tea (1-2 cups 41.2%) in their daily diet. The ANOVA results for the frequency of turmeric tuber, turmeric powder and ginger intake with BMI reveal that the intake was statistically not significant hence accepting the null hypothesis that there was no relationship between turmeric and

ginger intake on the BMI. The same analysis done with garlic among the different groups of BMI was significant ($p < 0.05$) (**Table- 2**). Hence, rejecting the null hypothesis, this establishes the relationship between the frequent dietary usage of immune boosting foods like garlic and a favourable effect on body weight among the selected college going students.

The study is not without limitations. A larger sample size may have shown promising statistically significant results. The age group could have covered all adults to get a clearer picture of the results.

Conclusion

Immune boosting foods (turmeric, ginger and garlic), when frequently consumed may be beneficial in maintaining a normal body weight among the selected college going students. It can be extrapolated to suggest that the inclusion of these immune boosting foods amongst various population groups diligently, and frequently in people who are overweight or obese may bring about favourable outcomes in their weight. Targeted prevention with the holistic use of these immune boosting foods will facilitate to bring about a reduction in malnutrition status across the population. More exploration in this area could open up avenues for detailed studies on the relationship between immune parameters and the BMI across population groups.

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